

A Kinetic Study of the Solvent Effect of Aquo-Aprotic Solvent System on the Therapeutic Uses of a Heavy Salicylate and its Hydrolysis Products

Prem Chand Kumar Sinha¹ and R. T. Singh³

1. Assistant Professor, Department of Chemistry, H. D. Jain College, Ara

2. Professor & Formerly HOD Chemistry and the Dean of the Faculty of Science,
V. K. S. University, Ara

Received: Aug 29, 2025

Accepted: Sep 27, 2025

Published: Oct 4, 2025

ABSTRACT

For highlighting the solvent effect of a peculiar dipolar aprotic solvent, DMF on the medicinal efficiency of Salicylate ester, the kinetic studies of the alkali catalysed solvolysis of Butyl Salicylate in aquo-DMF medium of various compositions starting from 30 to 80 vol.% of DMF at temperatures ranging from 20 to 40°C have been carried out. The specific rate constant values were found to decrease with increasing proportion of DMF at all the temperatures and thus the prediction of Parker has not been found applicable. The numerical values of iso-composition activation energy (E_C) and iso-dielectric energy (E_D) were found to be changed in opposite direction to each other. The values of iso-composition energy of the reaction are found to increase with increasing concentration of DMF in reaction media. On the other hand, the values of iso-dielectric activation energy were found decreasing with increasing the dielectric constant value of the reaction media. These changes observed in the two types of activation energies have been interpreted in the light of solvation and desolvation of initial and transition states to different extent. Variations in thermodynamic activations

parameters ΔS^* , ΔH^* and ΔG^* have also been evaluated and interpreted on the basis of specific solvation taking place in the reaction media.

From the evaluated value of iso-kinetic temperature of the reaction, which is 336.7, it is inferred that is strong solvent-solute interaction water-DMF media.

KEYWORDS: Therapeutic uses, Efficiency, Salicylate ester, Electrostatic effect, Iso-dielectric, Iso-composition, Activation parameters, Solvation phenomenon, Mobile transition state, Solvent-Solute Interaction.

INTRODUCTION

The effect of solvent on the alkali catalysed hydrolysis of esters have received a large number of attention from time to time¹⁻², but the explanations put forward for them are not satisfactory. Considering ester hydrolysis as ion-dipole type and assuming the predominance of electrostatic effects, Ingold³ as well as Laidler have predicted a decrease in rate with decreasing dielectric constant of the medium, for which there is general experimental evidence. However, on the basis of solvation phenomenon, Parker⁵ predicted a rate

enhancement in case of ester hydrolysis by dipolar-aprotic solvents like DMSO etc. and this view has been supported by Roberts⁶. However, the decrease in rate of ester hydrolysis upon addition of these solvents has also been observed earlier⁷⁻⁹ and recently¹⁰ and therefore, more works are needed to establish the mechanism of solvation and the effect of dielectric constant. Among the esters studied thoroughly so far, the esters having medicinal efficiency like salicylates appear to have received very little attention in this regard. Therefore, it is thought worthwhile to study the effect of a typical dipolar aprotic solvent DMF on the rate as well as on the various activation parameters of alkali catalysed hydrolysis of Butyl Salicylate at different temperatures to arrive at some definite conclusions regarding the effect of DMF on the medicinal potential of salicylate particularly in removing the joint pain of living being.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were either of BDH (AnalR) or Merck (CP) grade and all were purified before their use. The kinetics of alkali catalysed hydrolysis of Butyl Salicylate was studied in water-DMF media having varying concentration of DMF from 30 to 80% (v/v) at five different temperatures ranging from 20 to 40°C. The strength of reaction mixture was fixed 0.1 M and 0.5 M with respect to alkali (NaOH) and ester respectively.

The reaction was found to obey second order kinetic equation and the evaluated value of specific rate constants have been recorded in Table-

I. The value of iso-composition activation energy (E_c), iso-dielectric activation energy (E_D) and thermodynamic activation parameters of the reaction have been enlisted in Table – II, III and IV respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Solvent Effect on the Rate of Reaction:

From Table – I, it is obvious that rate constant values are markedly decreasing with the progressive addition of DMF at all the temperatures. Since DMF has a lower dielectric constant value than water, the bulk dielectric constant of the medium will be found to decrease and this will disfavour the formation of the higher polar transition state.

DMF being a poor anion solvent¹⁰, its increase in the aqueous mixture will naturally facilitate the desolvation of ions already solvated by water, forming a DMF water associated species¹¹. Since the initial and transition states (all being anions differing in size and charge) cannot be equally desolvated, the rate will naturally be effected by such specific solvation changes. Experimentally it has been observed that the rate decreases with increasing DMF in the medium and thus, it appears that the phenomenon of desolvation is more dominant in the transition state than that in the initial state and that is why the activation energy has been found to increase. Similar findings have also been reported earlier by Singh & Kumari¹², Singh and Singh¹³ and recently by K. Sushma¹⁴.

Effect of Temperature and Solvent on the Iso-Composition Activation Energy

Rate constant values of the reaction were found to increase with increasing temperature in accordance to the Arrhenius law, yielding a good straight line for the plots of $\log k$ against $1/T$. The E_{exp} or E_c (Iso-composition activation energy) values are shown in Table – II. The E_c values increase from 104.63 to 129.96 kJ/mol with increasing proportion of DMF from 30 to 80% (v/v) in the reaction media.

The probable cause for enhancement in the value of iso-composition activation energy of the reaction is desolvation and solvation of the transition and initial states respectively, which is also supported by the increase in the values of entropy of activation as recorded in Table – IV. Such findings and their interpretations have also been supported earlier by Singh et. al.¹⁵ and Singh & Mishra et. al.¹⁶ and in recent years by Sushma & Singh et al.¹⁷.

Solvent Effect on the Iso-dielectric Activation Energy (E_D) of the reaction

The values of iso-dielectric activation energy (E_D) of the reaction at different desired dielectric constant values of the media have been evaluated by the process reported by Elsemongy et. al.¹⁸ and are recorded in Table – III.

From the values recorded in Table – III, it is obvious that E_D values are found to decrease from 134.23 to 107.45 kJ/mol with increasing D values from 55 to 70 respectively of the reaction media. This

trend of change (depletion) in E_D values is in harmony with the enhancement in E_c values with increasing concentration of DMF in the reaction media.

Such findings are quite natural and are supported by the earlier reports of Dubey & Singh¹⁹ and Singh & Kumari et. al.²⁰ and also in the recent reports by Ajeet & Singh et. al.²¹.

Solvent effect on Thermodynamic Activation Parameters of the reaction

The evaluated consolidated values of the thermodynamic activation parameters, ΔH^* , ΔS^* and ΔG^* are mentioned in Table – IV. The increase in ΔG^* is a sign of specific desolvation of the transition state. This is in agreement with our view that the transition state is less solvated or desolvated with addition of DMF in the mixture. Elsemongy and Cleve²² have observed a similar increase in ΔG^* values. Thus from Table – IV, it is apparent that ΔH^* and ΔS^* values of the reaction are increasing with simultaneous enhancement in ΔG^* values. According to one of the fundamental thermodynamic equations:

$$\Delta G^* = \Delta H^* - T\Delta S^*$$

the above noted observation is only possible when enhancement in ΔH^* is greater than that observed in ΔS^* and thus the reaction is enthalpy dominating. Such observations and inferences have been found to be supported by the past reports of Singh & Kumari²³ and also in the recently reported findings of Raghaw & Singh²⁴.

Obedience of Barclay-Butler Rule and Solvent-solute interaction in Water-DMF Reaction Media:

As recorded in Table – IV, both the values of ΔH^* and ΔS^* are found increasing and the increase being quite smooth. Iso-kinetic relationship between ΔH^* and ΔS^* are obeying Barclay-Butler²⁵ rule giving an excellent straight line when ΔH^* is plotted against ΔS^* . The numerical value of the slope of the plots which determines the value of iso-kinetic temperature is found to be 336.70.

The increase in ΔH^* and ΔS^* values suggests the formation of more mobile transition state which supports the contention of desolvation of the transition state. On the guidelines of Leffler²⁶, from the evaluated value of iso-kinetic temperature of the reaction which is greater than 300 (336.70), it is inferred that there is appreciable change in the structure of the reactant or in the solvent or in both the reactant and the solvent due to much stronger interaction between solvent and solute present in the water-DMF reaction media.

Similar observations and inferences have also been reported recently by Sabita & Singh²⁷ and Raghaw & Singh²⁸.

Effect of Ionic strength on the rate of reaction:

There is negligible influence of the ionic strength on the reaction rate. This suggest that the reaction is not ion-ion, but ion-molecular in nature.

References:

1. Elsemongy, M.M.: Z. Physik. Chem. (Neue Folge), **95**, 215, 1975
2. Singh, Lallan, Singh, R. T. and Jha, R. C.: J. Indian Chem. Soc., **55**, 375, 1978
3. Ingold C. K.: Structure and Mechanism in Organic Chemistry, Bell, London, 1953
4. Laidler, K. J. and Lanskroener, P.A.: Trans Faraday Soc., **52**, 200, 1956
5. Parker, A. J.: Chem. Rev. **69**, 1, 1960
6. Roberts, D. D.: J. Org. Chem., **31**, 4037, 1966
7. Radhakrishnmurthy, P. S., and Patro, P. C.: Tetrahedron, **26**, 5503, 1970
8. Singh, Lallan, Singh, R. T. and Jha, R. C.: J. Indian Chem. Soc., **57**, 1089, 1980
9. Singh, Lallan, Singh, R. T. and Jha, R. C.: Ibid, **58**, 966, 1981
10. Parker, A. J.: Quatr. Rev., **16**, 163, 1962
11. Wolford, R. K.: J. Phys. Chem., **68**, 3392, 1964
12. Singh, R. T., Kumari, A., Kumari, R. and Kumari, P.: NIRJ Sci., **10**, 87 – 97, 2012
13. Singh, R. T., Singh, P. K., Singh, S. M., and Singh, U. C.: ARJ Phys. Sci., **15**, No. (1-2), 129 – 139, 2012
14. K. Sushma: WHJJ, **XVI**, No. (IX), 125-140, Sept. 2020
15. Singh, R. T., Singh, S. N., Singh, P., and Singh, R. I.: NIRJ Sci., **8**, 133 – 138, 2012
16. Singh, R. T., Mishra, S. K., Singh, S. B., and Singh, S.: ARJ Phys. Sci., **15**, No. (1-2), 141 – 150, 2012
17. K. Sushma, A. Abhay, Singh R. and Singh R. T.: IJAEMA, **XII**, No. (I), 3345-3363, Jan. 2020
18. Elsemongy, M.M., Elamayem, M.S. and Moussa, M.N.H. : Z. Physik. Chem., (Neue Folge), **95**, 215, 1975

19. Dubey, R., Singh, A. K., Singh, P. and Singh, R. T.: NIRJ Sci., **4**, 121-126, 2010
20. Singh, R. T., Kumar, A., Singh, S., and Kumari, V.: NIRJ Sci., **12**, 53-66, 2013
21. S. Ajeet, Singh R. and Singh R. T.: WHJJ, **XVIII**, No. (V), 67-83, May 2022
22. Cleve, N. J.: Soumen Kemi, **45B**, 235, 285, 1972
23. Singh R. T., Kumari V., Singh, M.. and Kumari, N.: NIRJ Sci., **13**, 59-63, 2013
24. K. Raghaw, and Singh, R. T.: Gradiva Research Journal, **10**, No. (8), 365-373, 2023
25. Barclay, I. A. and Butler, J. A. V.: Trans Faraday Soc., **34**, 1445, 1938
26. Leffler J. E. : Org. Chem., **20**, 1201, 1955
27. K. Sabita and Singh R. T.: GIS Science Journal, **10**, No. (8), 569-575, 2023
28. K. Raghaw and Singh R. T.: Journal of Xidian University, **9**, No. (1), 87-94, 2025

Table - I**Specific rate constant values of Alkali Catalysed Hydrolysis of Butyl Salicylate in Water-DMF media**

$$k \times 10^3 \text{ in } (dm)^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$$

Temp in °C	% of DMF (v/v)					
	30%	40%	50%	60%	70%	80%
20°C	56.29	44.88	36.64	29.25	23.81	17.74
25°C	111.71	96.36	79.03	65.74	54.94	42.54
30°C	228.88	196.43	71.83	147.16	128.00	109.91
35°C	426.27	393.37	353.83	315.21	279.96	230.25
40°C	869.16	794.15	732.99	674.37	613.34	524.93

Table - II**Iso-composition Activation Energy (E_c or E_{exp}) of the reaction**

% of DMF (v/v)	30%	40%	50%	60%	70%	80%
E_{exp} value of kJ/mol	104.63	108.88	114.85	120.18	123.23	129.96

Table - III**Iso-composition Activation Energy (E_D) of the reaction.**

D values of Aquo-DMF mixture	D=55	D=57.5	D=60	D=62.5	D=65	D=67.5	D=70
E_D kJ/mol	134.93	127.97	125.42	122.96	114.85	111.19	107.45

Table – IV**Activation Parameters of Alkali Catalysed Hydrolysis of Butyl Salicylate in Water-DMF solvent system** **ΔH^* and ΔG^* in kJ/mol, ΔS^* in J/K/mol**

% of DMF (v/v)	Mole% of DMF	ΔH^* in kJ/mol	20°C		25°C		30°C		35°C		40°C	
			ΔG^*	ΔS^*								
30%	9.12	103.35	83.08	69.18	82.86	68.75	82.49	68.84	82.18	68.73	81.82	68.78
40%	13.58	106.32	83.65	77.37	83.23	77.48	82.87	77.39	82.50	77.34	82.05	77.53
50%	18.96	112.27	84.15	95.97	83.72	95.80	83.16	96.07	82.77	95.77	82.27	95.84
60%	25.98	117.50	84.69	111.97	84.18	111.81	83.60	111.88	83.07	111.78	82.48	116.88
70%	35.27	122.48	85.18	127.30	84.68	126.84	83.95	126.16	83.37	126.98	82.72	127.02
80%	49.28	126.19	85.91	137.47	85.26	137.35	84.34	138.12	83.87	137.40	83.13	137.57